

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENT CONSCIOUSNESS

Sa'dulloyeva Mohinurbegim

Osiyo Xalqaro Universiteti pedagogika psixologiya
yo'nalishi magistranti

ANNOTATION

This article covers the development, formation and types of consciousness according to the theory of psychology, as well as specific social psychological methods for the development of student consciousness, the most active layer of society.

Keywords: *mind, psycho-physical, psizo-biological, phenomenon, materialistic orientation, intuition, imagination, will, memory, mental image of consciousness.*

Consciousness is the supreme form of psychic activity. It is a human-only phenomenon. The question of consciousness, its essence is one of the oldest problems. Those who initially tried to explain consciousness within the framework of religious and mythological views. The religious explanation of consciousness is based on its interpretation in the form of a divine phenomenon, a miracle created by God. In many religions, human consciousness is characterized in the form of manifestation of the great divine Mind. The roots of such views are very old. although they still have many supporters of their own. Whoever recognizes that the universe and Man are created, believes that consciousness is also the power of the creator.

In interpreting the essence of consciousness, direction 2 is the understanding that consciousness is reflected in the material world in the human brain, interpreting it in connection with the activities of the human body. At the same time, within the framework of such approaches, which received the name of the materialistic direction, cases of distorted interpretation of the essence of consciousness also appeared.

According to current figures, who have come to be known as Vulgar materialism, just as the liver produces saf-Rony, the brain produces mind absorption. The result of this approach is the conclusion that consciousness is not an ideal, but a material phenomenon. Although bile can be seen, the mind cannot be seen or caught. In fact, the history of consciousness is associated with the history of the beginning of a person's formation as a person. Since man is both a biological and a social being, it means that consciousness is a product of both biological and social progress. Consciousness is made up of the senses, senses, imagination, will, and Karash of human thought. Self-awareness, memory, will, speech are the main aspects of consciousness.

Modern science recognizes that the mind matter is the result of an ongoing evolution. Matter, nature has existed all the time, and man is a product of the relatively recent progress of the material world. It took several millions of years for the progress of matter, the emergence of a person who can think. Consciousness is a product of the development of nature, a property of matter, not all matter, but the product of matter, that is, the human brain, which is formed at a higher level. But it is not enough for the mind to have only the brain dividing itself. Consciousness is closely connected with the natural and social environment that surrounds a person and is able to function under the influence of this environment.

In modern times, electronic machines have been created that also carry out complex creative processes, but they cannot replace consciousness, since consciousness is an extremely complex objective existence.¹ It is obvious that it is impossible to improve the effectiveness of teaching in a higher school without introducing into the system of instructions, tools and methods of teaching and teaching lessons, which are used in the educational process, the peculiarities of the Uzbek people, the culture of treatment, the masterpieces of value and culture, its improvement, the theory of Oriental Education The feeling of faith, faith, patriotism, purity, conscientiousness, truthfulness, responsibility and duty cannot be composed without a national feeling, national character, National image, taste, etc.,

¹ Aktov, Abdulla. O'zME.Birinchi jild.Toshkent, 2000-yil

which has a history of several decades, even going to the level of Unitarianism, along with the rational and productive use of the progressive ideas of World Culture and education. To teach the people to overcome the material and spiritual difficulties of social life, it is important to bring the Qur'an from the Karim, the Khadis. Therefore, it is necessary to mature people of faith and faith by harmonizing some aspects of religious education with secular education.

To do this, it is important to establish educational work taking into account psychological characteristics in the spiritual formation of students, in which, based on upbringing, it is chosen that attention is primary.

It is known that each nation finds its own identity, national culture, literature, language and expression in the complex of the spiritual (spiritual) style of that nation, that is, in the spirit of the nation.

The Uzbek people are distinguished by their spiritual image, national character, national character, feeling, client (tempramenti), behavior, taste, taste. Uzbek milati's cognitive processes (intuition, perception, imagination, memory, thinking, imagination), ability to focus on a specific direction, need and interest, national consciousness have their own characteristics.

Consciousness is a known, substance-specific world model. Awareness is based on the process by which the development of consciousness takes place, it is presented in a construction order, uniting parts into one whole, based on the available information and knowledge. The final rule of information and knowledge processing.

The law of the development of consciousness No. 1: develops through the perception of information and knowledge accumulated through contact with the environment.

The law of the development of consciousness No. 2: consciousness develops when a cause –and-effect relationship is established, which makes it possible to transform dependence into a relationship. 1-the law of consciousness: it arises when the mind combines parts into one whole energy that increases energy to a person along with the

release of energy can manifest itself as Joy, an increase in strength. Awareness Law 2: collecting information before awareness .

The law of awareness of No. 3: understanding simple patterns with single available information performed necessary for understanding.

In the process of education and upbringing, scattering the seeds of knowledge about the history of our republic, culture, jahangashta people who have grown up from our distant ancestors, scientists, thinkers, enlighteners creates a feeling of pride and pride in students and students.

The opening of science techniques, fertile mother soil, sahiy and hardworking people, minerals, cotton, silk, blackberries, gold in the world and nationwide market will grow national consciousness in students, improve spiritual self – awareness. Accelerates social activity, leads them towards creative search, increases interest in acquiring the foundations of science.

In the past, Uzbek made the most effective use of methods of National Education, riddles, problems, resourcefulness exercises for creativity develop students ‘ mental activity, act as mind-blowing exercises, cultivate their moral abilities. In the educational work of the Higher School, national traditions, rituals, paintings, holidays (Navruz, Uzbek language Day, Independence Day, golden autumn, seedling season, melon sayli, grape sayli, Harvest Festival, cotton Festival, views of sumac and Uzbek cuisine), to some extent find their place, most effectively affect students, since common characters are harmonized with demanding activities, mustakham is encouraged to live as a community.

The social participation of students in these works increases activity in them, each person tests his abilities and skills. The participation of students in such activities makes up such qualities as Independence, Initiative, Organization in them. In the process of education, the formation of folk masterpieces in the minds of students, rational measures of national values, focusing on that which shape their spiritual world.

Spiritual is the main basis of the development of not only man, but also the state and society. Spiritual renewal should be a deep study of the rich national – spiritual heritage of the people, a special way of living and contemplation of the mill, the education of the younger generation in the spirit of these traditions, traditions, respect for our ancestors.

The student period is considered one of the characteristic complex stages of adolescence, since it is during this period that professional knowledge, skills, as well as important professional qualities in a person are also found in the composition. The problem of the formation of professional qualities as a student has been studied within the framework of a number of studies.

Many world and foreign scientists say that today the formation of professional qualities is rising to the first place among human needs according to its level of relevance. This problem is associated with a complex of problems of social theory and practice, and is located from the central part of psychology. Individual types of professional qualities in students are studied, which change under the influence of economic, social, socio-cultural conditions. In modern research, professional qualities in students are distinguished as the main criterion for the professional development of the individual and as the leading character of the subject of Labor. This point of view is considered to be a logical coverage of the development of the existing criteria for professional development in World psychology from the level of productive activity of the employee to the level of characteristic of the specialist. As a subject of work, a specialist, unlike an employee, sets the goal of his activity himself, determines the path and means of achieving it, takes responsibility for the result of the activity. He fully manages activities, knows ways out of various practical situations, has the ability to organize activities, anticipate its changes and progress. In the professional formation of students, professional qualities and progress are closely linked: professional qualities are formed in the process of professional development on the one hand, and are an important indicator of the manifestation of an individual as a specialist on the other. In practical terms, this means: in order to have its reputation in a new socio-economic

dynamic, not to break in competition, to ensure a prosperous future, the future specialist, that is, the student, must be in constant development, and, moreover, analyze his position in social and labor conditions. Therefore, the modern direction of research on professional qualities is the study of aspects related to the process of social and professional development of an individual.

Professional formation as a transformation of a student into a specialist is a change in a person's perception of himself, about his position in the professional and social environment, moreover, the formation of new professional qualities in himself, in broad terms-in harmony with the professional self-awareness of the individuality is a process that takes place. During crises of professional formation, professional qualities are clearly manifested. Foreign sources indicate two directions in relation to the study of the problem of the formation of professional qualities in students: the first is aimed at professional development, the individual's work on himself, and the second is focused on the social aspects and factors of professional formation. Spiritual and moral education plays an important role in the spiritual formation of students. The main goal of spiritual and moral education gives students the opportunity to find their place in social life, to mature themselves, to determine their own destiny, to create. In spiritual and moral education lies the spiritual and moral formation of students on the basis of universal, national values. This is crucial in fulfilling the mission of the educational process. Strengthening the independence of the country, the fate of its reforms in socio-political, economic, military, legal and other spheres, the establishment of the future of the country depends on the level of spiritual and moral upbringing, high consciousness, social activity of student youth. "The fate of progress," said Our president, "is decided by spiritually mature people. Technical knowledge, the ability to master complex technology should go along with spiritual perfection, independent thinking. Mental intelligence and spiritual potential are two wings of an enlightened person." So that every student, youth (student) today has spiritual immunity. It is necessary to have a deep understanding of his sacred duties to the motherland and the people, to be able to fight against any situations of immorality that

occur in society. Today the whole world is not power, the mind is going to a battle of thought and ideas. And the peak of contemplation is reached through spirituality. A student who has become the goal of spirituality, and young people strive to never be inferior in the world, No one, in any field. At no time does a person's spiritual vision take shape on its own, in an empty place. Historical, educational and in its formation and development the role of social factors, especially spiritual education in the family and family, is incomparable. The family is a spiritual stronghold that leads young people towards maturity. Currently, with the formation of a spiritually mature person in the educational system, it is possible to achieve the socio – economic progress of society. To this end, pedagogical tools and forms of the formation of student – youth spirituality of Higher Education and folk education have been developed. One of the social foundations of the formation of student spirituality is the mutual unity of the Family, School (College, University) and neighborhood, teaching based on the rich national cultural, historical traditions of the people, Customs, universal values also pays off.

The fate and development of society is considered in many ways in the hands of students of Higher Education, that is, Taurus specialists. Therefore, it is necessary to educate students on the basis of socio – psychological foundations that form spiritually.